

Data management plan (DMP)

Targeted Stimulation to Disrupt Glioblastoma Invasion

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	16/10/2025	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project

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FWF Data Management Plan (DMP)

I General Information							
I.1 Administrative information	<p>PI: Marta Nowakowska-Desplantes, marta.nowakowska@medunigraz.at, Data Collector, Data Curator, Data Manager, Project Leader</p> <p>FWF Grant-DOI: 10.55776/ESP2798525</p> <p>Internal Project ID: available once the contract is signed</p> <p>DMP version: 1.0, 25/02/2026</p> <p>Contributors:</p> <p>Supervisor, Research Group, Rainer Schindl, rainer.schindl@medunigraz.at</p>						
I.2 Data management responsibilities and resources	<p>Person responsible for data management and DMP: Marta Nowakowska-Desplantes, marta.nowakowska@medunigraz.at</p> <p>Co-ordination of data management responsibilities across partners: Marta Nowakowska-Desplantes, marta.nowakowska@medunigraz.at</p> <p>Resources costed in for RDM: There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.</p>						
II Data Characteristics							
II.1 Data description and collection or re-use of existing data	Produced datasets:						
	dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data	description
	P1	Fluorescent images	Images	.tiff, .png, .jpg	100 - 1000 MB	no	
	P2	Calcium imaging traces	Structured text	.csv	<100 MB	no	
	P3	Calcium imaging videos	Audiovisual data	.avi, .mp4	1 - 5 GB	no	
P4	FACS data	Raw data	.fcs	<100 MB	no		

	<p>Methods and software used for data generation and reuse</p> <p>Data will be generated using fluorescent microscopy and appropriate software (Live Acquisition for calcium imaging, NIS-Elements for confocal microscopy, ZEN for CellDiscoverer). Calcium imaging traces will be generated using Offline Analysis software and analysed with customised R scripts.</p>
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III Documentation and Data Quality

<p>III.1 Metadata and documentation</p>	<p>Data organisation, metadata, and documentation:</p> <p>The filenames will follow the project naming convention and include a timestamp of creation:</p> <pre> /project_name/ /raw_data/ /YYYYMMDD_experimentID/ /calcium imaging/ or /stimulation_logs/ or /FACS/, etc. /processed_data/ /YYYYMMDD_experimentID/ /analysis_results/ /figures/ /documentation/ </pre> <p>Where applicable, established community formats will be adopted, e.g. for microscopy data: OME-TIFF. In case no domain-specific metadata standards are applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used at dataset level. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.</p> <p>Version control will start with V followed by at least 2 digits placed as the last element. For major revisions we will use V01 -> V99 convention, while for minor revisions, we will add to digits after a hyphen, e.g. V01-03.</p> <p>Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.</p> <p>As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.</p> <p>All preprocessing, signal analysis, and statistical steps will be documented in detail using R scripts. The scripts will include annotations describing each step of the workflow. Each dataset will include a structured file describing the experimental setup, stimulation parameters (e.g., pulse duration, intensity, frequency), recording conditions, and naming conventions. Upon publication, datasets and analysis scripts will be deposited in an open-access repository (e.g., Zenodo). Documentation will include detailed descriptions of stimulation protocols, glioma models, and analysis methods to enable reuse in related studies.</p>
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III.2 Data quality control	<p>Data quality control:</p> <p>The following data quality checks will be done: calibration, repeated samples or measurements and standardised data capture.</p>
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IV Data Storage, Sharing, and Long-Term Preservation

IV.1 Data storage and backup during the research process	<p>Storage and backup facilities:</p> <p>For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Marta Nowakowska-Desplantes (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the system operator. The data will be stored on the servers of our institution.</p> <p>P1 (Fluorescent images), P2 (Calcium imaging traces), P3 (Calcium imaging videos), P4 (FACS data) will be stored on NextCloud (https://box.medunigraz.at): Med Uni Graz NextCloud is used to synchronize data between different devices (PC, notebook, cell phone, etc.) and to exchange data between persons. The data is stored on the servers of the Medical University of Graz. Data transfer to the NextCloud server is always encrypted (encryption takes place using HTTPS). The data on the server itself is not encrypted, but is protected by access rights. The server is backed up in accordance with the Med Uni Graz guidelines (daily and weekly backup, 3 months storage, locally separated).</p> <p>Data security and protection of sensitive data:</p> <p>We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at our institution, and the DMP will be updated.</p> <p>Access to data during research:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="439 871 1644 1222"> <thead> <tr> <th>dataset ID</th> <th>selected project members</th> <th>all other project members</th> <th>the public</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>P1</td> <td>writing</td> <td>reading only</td> <td>no access</td> </tr> <tr> <td>P2</td> <td>writing</td> <td>reading only</td> <td>no access</td> </tr> <tr> <td>P3</td> <td>writing</td> <td>reading only</td> <td>no access</td> </tr> <tr> <td>P4</td> <td>writing</td> <td>reading only</td> <td>no access</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.</p>	dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public	P1	writing	reading only	no access	P2	writing	reading only	no access	P3	writing	reading only	no access	P4	writing	reading only	no access
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P4	writing	reading only	no access																		

IV.2 Data sharing and long-term preservation

Data publication and access conditions:

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	2028-08-31	Zenodo	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P2	Open	2028-08-31	Zenodo	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P3	Open	2028-08-31	Zenodo	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P4	Open	2028-08-31	Zenodo	DOI	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

ZENODO builds and operates a simple and innovative service that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to share and showcase multidisciplinary research results (data and publications) that are not part of the existing institutional or subject-based repositories of the research communities. ZENODO enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to: easily share the long tail of small research results in a wide variety of formats including text, spreadsheets, audio, video, and images across all fields of science. display their research results and get credited by making the research results citable and integrate them into existing reporting lines to funding agencies like the European Commission. easily access and reuse shared research results. <https://zenodo.org/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: The data will be provided in standard formats making it available to view and analyse it with free and open-source software, such as Fiji/ImageJ, QuPath, CytoFlow, or RStudio.

Long-term preservation and deletion of data:			
dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	Zenodo	10 years	<p>The primary target audience for the datasets generated in this project includes researchers working at the interface of neuroscience, oncology, and biomedical engineering.</p> <p>1) Cancer Neuroscience researchers: Scientists investigating glioma interactions and brain–tumor communication mechanisms could reuse the data to compare imaging patterns under different stimulation conditions.</p> <p>2) Bioelectronics researchers: Teams developing novel stimulation or recording technologies benefit from detailed calcium imaging datasets and data on stimulation parameters to optimise device design and protocols.</p> <p>3) Computational scientists: The structured datasets containing stimulation-response relationships could be reused for computational modeling of glioma network activity.</p>
P2	Zenodo	10 years	
P3	Zenodo	10 years	
P4	Zenodo	10 years	

V Legal and Ethical Aspects

V.1 Legal aspects	<p>Personal data:</p> <p>At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at our institution, and the DMP will be updated.</p>
	<p>Intellectual property rights and rights of use:</p> <p>The following individual(s) hold rights and control access to the project data: For the duration of the project: Principal Investigator (Marta Nowakowska-Desplantes) – full rights to all datasets, analysis code, and documentation</p> <p>responsible for authorising access and approving data sharing. Supervisor (Rainer Schindl) and collaborators – read/write access to relevant datasets required for joint analysis or publication. Students or technical personal – access limited to specific experimental folders or data types as required for their assigned tasks. After publication or upon project completion, datasets will be made publicly available through a trusted repository (e.g., Zenodo) under a suitable open license (e.g., CC BY 4.0).</p>

V.2 Ethical aspects	Ethical issues: No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.
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